

Rac-4e

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-165-rac-20%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	7	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 165 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/27/2021 4:44:51 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/28/2021 10:38:02 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.433	5790110	49.98	537731
2	8.884	5793880	50.02	437297

Asy-4e

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-166-20%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	8	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 166
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	20.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/28/2021 10:22:25 AM CST		
Date Processed:	10/28/2021 10:40:12 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.313	663477	3.50	60154
2	8.732	18299106	96.50	1440726